

INVESTIGATION OF THE STATE ANXIETY LEVELS OF KICKBOXING COACHES ACCORDING TO CERTAIN VARIABLES

Eyyup Yildirim¹,

Atalay Gacar

Fırat University,

Faculty of Sports Sciences,

Elazığ, Turkey

Abstract:

The aim of this study is to investigate the state anxiety levels experienced by kickboxing coaches according to certain variables. The population of the study consists of 84 coaches who participated in the kickboxing coaching course conducted in Elazığ in 2018 while the sample of the study consists of 79 coaches who participated in this course. In the study, a personal information form to collect data from the participating coaches and the "Trait Anxiety Scale", which was developed by Spilberger, to determine the trait anxiety levels of coaches were adopted. The adopted scale was developed by Spielberg et al. in order to determine the trait anxiety levels of individuals and it was adapted into Turkish by Oner and Le Compte (1997), which consists of 20 matters. In the analysis of the collected data in the study, parametric tests were conducted and the data was interpreted in SPSS 24.00 package software. Then, for the significant differences observed in the results of frequency distribution, arithmetic mean, percentage, t-test and One-Way ANOVA, Tukey test was conducted in order to determine which groups contained the difference. As a result of the study, for the participating coach candidates, it was determined that the individuals from the 19-21 years old group had higher levels of anxiety compared to other groups while individuals with a high school level of education and 1-4 years of experience as athletes had higher levels of anxiety compared to those with 5-9 years and 15 years or above experience as athletes.

Keywords: anxiety, sport, kickboxing, coaching

1. Introduction

In today's sports, the excellence in physical capacity does is not regarded sufficient to solely raise the sports performance to high levels. Athletes also have a psychological

¹ Correspondence: email eyildirim73@gmail.com

capacity and it should be considered as much as the physical aspect. For the athletes who experience emotional fluctuations, even when they are physically ready, the failure to meet the expected success can be explained in this way (Tavacioglu, 1999).

There are a number of psychological phenomena that affect the performance in sports. One of the most significant of these phenomena is anxiety. Anxiety is defined as *"a state that distresses and bothers people, and a state of tension that is mixed with insecurity"* (Oncul, 2000).

Today, the fact that sports gained an operability such as this has brought various psychological burdens to athletes and the necessity to scientifically discuss athletes as psycho-social beings arose. Sports scientists intensely endeavor in increasing sports performance. Novel principles of training are investigated and the search for improving athletes' performances continues. All these search and studies demonstrated that the physical capacity was not solely sufficient in sports performance and psychological capacity was a factor that should not be underestimated (Akarçeşme, 2004).

Anxiety is classified into two parts as state anxiety and trait anxiety. The state anxiety is defined as *"a type of anxiety that is based on a state that is temporarily experienced by every individual, which arises from stress depending on the environmental conditions, is mostly based on logical reasons and can be understood by others"* (Oner & Compte, 1983; Selya, 1998; Kuru, 2000).

Trait anxiety is defined as *"perceiving the stress-causing circumstance as dangerous or threatening and increasing in frequency and intensity of the situational emotional reactions against this threat, and its gaining continuity"* (Ozgüven, 2000).

Trait anxiety is not directly observed in individuals' behaviors. However, the intensity and the frequency of the situational emotional reactions detected at various times and under various conditions can be utilized. Certain people are constantly uneasy and unhappy. This originates from the person himself/herself and is a type of trait anxiety. Trait anxiety can be defined as an individuals' exposition of uneasiness, concern, pessimism, oversensitivity and intense emotive reactions, independent of the environmental conditions (Oner & Compte, 1983).

As a result of the trait anxiety, unhappiness, displeasure, pessimism, easy vulnerability are observed. These individuals also experience state anxiety more frequently and intensely compared to others. The intensity and the period of trait anxiety depend on the individual's personality structure. The difference in people's trait anxiety levels originates from the differences in the perception and the interpretation of the situations that are dangerous and threatening (Koknel, 1997).

The aim of this study is to investigate the trait anxiety levels experienced by kickboxing coaches according to certain variables.

2. Material and Method

In our study, it was aimed to investigate the trait anxiety levels of kickboxing coaches. The study was designed with the inspiration of the hypothesis of *"the trait anxiety levels of kickboxing coaches' trait anxiety levels differ according to certain variables"*.

The population of the study consists of 84 coaches who participated in the kickboxing coaching course conducted in Elazig in 2018 while the sample of the study consists of 79 coaches who participated in this course.

In the study, a personal information form to collect data from the participating coaches and the "Trait Anxiety Scale", which was developed by Spilberger, to determine the trait anxiety levels of coaches were adopted. The adopted scale was developed by Spielberg et al. in order to determine the trait anxiety levels of individuals and it was adapted into Turkish by Oner and Le Compte (1997). The scale, consisting of 20 matters, was conducted with the kickboxers face to face. The data scale consists of 37 matters. The first 17 matters of the scale cover the personal information while the other 20 matters cover the test that measures the trait anxiety levels of athletes (Oner & Compte, 1997).

In the calculation of the anxiety scores, observing the previous studies, the matters 1, 6, 7, 10, 13, 16 and 19 were evaluated as -1, -2, -3 and -4 during scoring according to the provided answers while other matters were scored as 1, 2, 3 and 4. Then, the 35 base points were added, creating the trait anxiety score.

Parametric tests were conducted for the data analysis of the study. The analyses were conducted by using SPSS 24.00 package software. With the help of SPSS, for the results of frequency distribution, arithmetic means, percentage, t-test and One-Way ANOVA test with significant differences, Tukey test was conducted in order to determine which groups contained the difference. The significance level was determined as 0.05.

3. Results

Table 1: The Distribution of Trait Anxiety Levels of Kickboxing Coach Candidates according to the Variable of Age

Age	N	X	Ss	F	p
19-21 years old	32	36,37	5,96	4,37	0,01
22-24 years old	25	43,68	5,17		
25 years old and above	22	40,68	9,63		
Total	79	43,93	7,26		

According to the ANOVA test results conducted with the age variable of the kickboxing coach candidates participated in the study, it was observed that there was a significant difference in the trait anxiety values. For this difference, it was observed that the individuals from the 19-21 years old group had higher levels of anxiety compared to those from other groups.

Table 2: The Distribution of Trait Anxiety Levels of Kickboxing Coach Candidates according to the Variable of Education

Education Level	N	X	Ss	F	p
High School	48	43,08*	7,69	3,23	0,04*
Associate's Degree	17	42,76	6,66		
Bachelor's Degree	14	48,28*	4,82		
Total	79	43,93	7,26		

According to the ANOVA test conducted with the education variable of the coach candidates participated in the survey, a significant difference was detected. According to this, coaches with high school degrees had higher levels of anxiety compared to those with bachelor's degrees.

Table 3: The Distribution of Trait Anxiety Levels of Kickboxing Coach Candidates according to the Variable of the period in sports

Period in Sports	N	X	Ss	F	p
1-4 years*	19	43,08*	5,05814	4,314	,007*
5-9 years *	30	42,76	5,73365		
10-14 years	16	48,28*	8,76713		
15 years and above**	14	43,93	8,53693		
Total	79	43,08*	7,26838		

According to the ANOVA test conducted with the period in sports variable of the coach candidates participated in the study, it was observed that individuals with 1-4 years' experience as athletes had higher anxiety levels compared to those with 5-9 years and 15 years and above experiences as athletes.

4. Discussion

According to the ANOVA test results conducted with the age variable of the kickboxing coach candidates participated in the study, it was observed that there was a significant difference in the trait anxiety values. For this difference, it was observed that the individuals from the 19-21 years old group had higher levels of anxiety compared to those from other groups. It could be concluded that the high anxiety levels and anxiety symptoms of the youth in this group compared to other age groups might be due to the fact that they are in their adolescence years, which is recognized with its unique psychological characteristics. Similar findings were observed in the study conducted by Nergüz Bozkurt in 2004, which aimed to determine the anxiety levels of university students (Bozkurt, 2004).

According to the ANOVA test conducted with the education variable of the coach candidates participated in the survey, a significant difference was detected. According to this, coaches with high school degrees had higher levels of anxiety compared to those with bachelor's degrees. Education, which is a process, is not only a period of acquiring knowledge but also an activity of people to create a better

awareness of the world and their own existence. Because with increasing level of education, the possibility of individuals approaching circumstances they experience calmer and more solution-oriented could be higher, it can be concluded that with the increasing education levels of the participant coach candidates in the study could lead them to have lower levels of anxiety. Similar results were found in the studies conducted regarding the anxiety levels of referees and the study exhibits parallelisms with our study (10, 11).

According to the ANOVA test conducted with the period in sports variable of the coach candidates participated in the study, it was observed that individuals with 1-4 years experiences as athletes had higher anxiety levels compared to those with 5-9 years and 15 years and above experiences as athletes.

In conclusion, for the participating coach candidates in the study, it was determined that the individuals from the 19-21 years old group had higher levels of anxiety compared to other groups while individuals with a high school level of education and 1-4 years of experience as athletes had higher levels of anxiety compared to those with 5-9 years and 15 years or above experience as athletes.

References

1. Tavacioglu, L. (1999). *Sports Psychology-Cognitive Evaluations*. Ankara: Bağırgan Publishing Company.
2. Oncul, R. (2000). *Dictionary of Education and Educational Sciences*. Ankara: M.E.B. Publications.
3. Akarcesme, C. (2004). The Relationship between the State Anxiety before the Volleyball Match and Performance Criteria, Master's Thesis, Gazi University Institute of Health Sciences, Ankara
4. Oner, N. & Le Compte, A. (1997). *Handbook of State Anxiety Trait Anxiety Inventory*. Istanbul: Boğaziçi University Publishing.
5. Selya, H. (1998). Stress without distress. (ed. Barbara Woods) *Applying psychology to sport*. Hodder & Stoughton, 98-109.
6. Kuru, E. (2000). *Psychology in Sports*. Ankara: G. Ü. Communication Faculty Press.
7. Ozguven, İ.E. (2000). *Psychological Tests*. Ankara: Pdrem Publishing.
8. Koknel, O. (1997). Personality from Anxiety to Happiness. 14. Issue, Altın Kitaplar Publishing, İstanbul, p. 20, 21, 23, 119.
9. Bozkurt N. (2004). The Relationship between Depression and Anxiety levels and Several Variables of a Group of University Students, *Education and Science*, Volume 29, Issue 133 p. 32-39.
10. Bayraktar G., Tekin M., Eroğlu H. & Cicioglu I. (2006). Investigation of the Anxiety Levels of International and National Wrestling Referees. Atatürk

University Physical Education and Sports Sciences Journal Volume: 8 Issue:4
Erzurum.

11. Karakaya, Y. E., Brusseau, T. & Karademir, T. (2015). The Relation Between Student Athletes Behaviour in the Classroom and Teachers Burnout Level. *Biomedical Human Kinetics*, 7(1), p. 163-170.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).